

This invited paper was presented as a keynote speech at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is included in the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

AUTHORS

Rita Abecasis
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9360-9293>

AFFILIATIONS

USF Baixa
ULS Sao Jose
Lisbon, Portugal

ABSTRACT

Social prescribing (SP) connects patients with community-based resources to address social determinants of health, significantly impacting primary healthcare globally. Originating in the UK, SP links patients to activities and services that tackle mental health, physical inactivity, and socioeconomic issues, reducing healthcare utilization and enhancing quality of life. Portugal has adopted SP through pilot projects and the Social Prescribing Portugal Network, aiming for national integration. Despite promising outcomes, evaluating SP's effectiveness remains complex due to intervention variability. Future research requires standardized methodologies to conclusively demonstrate SP's efficacy, underscoring its potential as a holistic, patient-centered approach to healthcare.

KEYWORDS

Primary health care, social determinants of health, community health services, patient-centered care

INTRODUCTION

General practitioners (GPs) spend nearly 19% of consultation time addressing non-medical concerns, impacting the time available for direct healthcare. 80% of health outcomes are shaped by social determinants of health (SDOH) such as education, income, physical environment, and lifestyle (Citizens Advice, 2015). SDOH have been shown to have a greater influence on health than either genetic factors or access to healthcare services (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2024).

The concept of addressing health needs through social means is not entirely new, with roots in community-focused initiatives that predate its formal recognition. However, the structured approach now known as social prescribing began to take shape in the late 20th century. In the United Kingdom, the Bromley by Bow Centre, established in 1984, pioneered a community-developed social prescribing model, demonstrating the potential of integrating social and medical approaches.

The past decade has witnessed a significant surge in the global interest and formalization of social prescribing. A major step forward was the integration of social prescribing into the NHS long-term plan (2019) as a key pillar of personalized care, with a commitment to fund link workers who connect people with various support and engagement opportunities. Other countries have also seen significant developments. The evolution of social prescribing models varies across different countries, reflecting their unique healthcare infrastructures and cultural contexts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This lecture is informed by a narrative review of relevant academic literature, policy reports, and documented case studies from countries with established social prescribing frameworks, notably the United Kingdom and Portugal. Sources were selected based on their relevance to contemporary primary care practice and their contribution to understanding the integration of social prescribing within healthcare systems. Thematic analysis was employed to synthesize key aspects related to the origin, development, implementation, and impact of social prescribing in the context of family medicine.

WHAT IS SOCIAL PRESCRIBING?

Social prescribing (SP) responds to the need to address these broader determinants. It connects individuals with community-based resources through referrals—typically made by GPs or other professionals—to Link

Workers, who help identify needs and suitable local services. SP promotes a person-centered approach, shifting the focus from “What’s the matter with you?” to “What matters to you?”

Globally, SP models can vary and are shaped by local healthcare systems and cultures.

IMPACT ON PATIENTS

Social isolation, mental health concerns, physical inactivity, and socioeconomic barriers: these are the pressing issues SP is targeting. Interventions such as walking groups or creative workshops complement traditional care and structured guidance also supports those facing unemployment, debt, or housing issues by connecting them with relevant services and community networks. As people engage in meaningful activities, their sense of purpose and autonomy grows, leading to better quality of life. Studies consistently report improvements in mental health among individuals participating in social prescribing programs. This includes reductions in symptoms of anxiety and depression, as well as a decrease in feelings of loneliness and social isolation. Engagement in social prescribing initiatives has also been linked to increased levels of physical activity and the adoption of healthier lifestyles. Referrals to exercise programs, walking groups, or gardening clubs can motivate individuals to become more physically active, which in turn has numerous benefits for both physical and mental health (Griffiths et al., 2022). Improvements in self-esteem and self-confidence are also frequently reported outcomes of social prescribing (Dayson et al., 2020). As individuals engage in new activities, develop new skills, and build connections with others, their sense of self-worth and ability to manage their own health can be significantly enhanced. Ultimately, these positive changes contribute to an overall improvement in patients' perceived quality of life and general well-being.

IMPACT ON THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM

An important aspect of SP is its impact in currently overburdened healthcare systems. Evidence, particularly from the UK, suggests SP can reduce GP visits, emergency attendances, and hospital admissions. Specifically, there was a 42.2% reduction in GP appointments among 1,751 patients who accessed social prescribing in Tameside and Glossop and a 15.4%–23.6% reduction in A&E attendances among 5,908 patients who accessed social prescribing in Kent (National Academy for Social Prescribing, 2024). Cost analyses indicate potential savings, though results are mixed and evaluation is complex due to the diversity of interventions.

IN PORTUGAL

In Portugal, a pilot project was launched by a young family doctor in 2018. The framework involves social workers as link workers and is starting to become an important resource of the national healthcare service. Since 2018 multiple projects have flourished all across the country, targeting different demographics: the elderly, the migrant community, pregnant women, young adults and children.

In 2024, a significant step towards the formalization and expansion of social prescribing in Portugal was the launch of the Social Prescribing Portugal Network by NOVA National School of Public Health, with the support of the Portuguese government. This network serves as a hub for technical-scientific consulting, training, and skills strengthening for professionals involved in social prescribing initiatives across the country. SP implementation seems simple, but the results show that in practice, it faces a complex intervention with multiple stakeholders, diverse community responses and factors influencing project success. The network aims to foster collaboration among researchers, professionals, service users, managers, and policymakers to enhance the effective and sustainable implementation of social prescribing in Portugal (National Academy for Social Prescribing, 2024).

IN TURKEY

For Turkey, considering the prevalent social and health needs, including rising rates of mental health issues and the challenges of an aging population and refugee integration, social prescribing presents a promising avenue to complement its existing healthcare system. While the level of formal implementation among Turkish GPs appears to be in its early stages, the fundamental principles of addressing social determinants of health through community-based interventions hold significant relevance.

DISCUSSION

Overall, the evaluation of social prescribing's efficacy and cost-effectiveness is challenged by the complexity and heterogeneity of the interventions, the diverse range of activities involved, and the difficulty in standardizing outcome measures across different studies and contexts. While there is a growing body of evidence suggesting potential benefits, particularly in areas like mental health and physical activity, and promising indicators of cost-effectiveness when considering broader social outcomes, there is a clear need for more rigorous research using standardized methodologies and outcome measures to strengthen the evidence base and provide more definitive conclusions.

CONCLUSION

The journey of social prescribing, from its early grassroots beginnings to its increasing integration into national healthcare policies, underscores a growing recognition of the limitations of purely biomedical models in addressing the complex health challenges of modern society. The example of Portugal, where a single-family doctor launched a growing movement, can inspire young doctors alike to take action and become true leaders in getting healthcare closer to what really matters to patients.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). (2024, January 17). *Social determinants of health (SDOH)*. <https://www.cdc.gov/about/priorities/why-is-addressing-sdoh-important.html>
- Citizens Advice. (2015, May). *A very general practice: How much time do GPs spend on issues other than health?* <https://www.citizensadvice.org.uk/about-us/policy/policy-research-topics/health-and-care-policy-research/a-very-general-practice/>
- Dayson, C., et al. (2020, March 28). Social prescribing for patients of secondary mental health services: Emotional, psychological and social well-being outcomes. *Journal of Public Mental Health, 19*(4). <https://doi.org/10.1108/jpmh-10-2019-0088>
- Griffiths, C., et al. (2022). Social prescribing through primary care: A systematic review of the evidence. *Open Journal of Preventive Medicine, 12*(2), 31–58. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojpm.2022.122003>
- National Academy for Social Prescribing. (2024). *The impact of social prescribing on health service use and costs: Examples of local evaluations in practice*. https://socialprescribingacademy.org.uk/media/ibtdvgn0/nasp_sp_impactonservice_nov24.pdf

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Rita Abecassis
USF Baixa
ULS Sao Jose
Lisbon, Portugal
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9360-9293>
rita.abecassis@ulssjose.min-saude.pt